

Transforming the Assessment Method of Multiple Classes: the Case of three Project Management Curricular Units at University of Minho

Anabela P. Tereso ¹

¹ ALGORITMI Centre, Department of Production and Systems, School of Engineering, University of Minho, Guimarães, Portugal

Email: anabelat@dps.uminho.pt

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Abstract

This paper presents an experience of transforming the assessment method of three curricular units on the subject of project management at the University of Minho, for different engineering courses, Integrated Project Management of the Master in Engineering Project Management and the Master in Chemical and Biological Engineering, and Industrial Project Management of the Master in Industrial Engineering and Management. This experience started with the author's participation in an initiative of IDEA-UMinho Centre to promote teaching and learning, named Assessment+. During the training, several assessment methods were introduced and the participants were asked to analyze a curricular unit and to propose a transformation of the assessment method. The one chosen was Integrated Project Management of the Master in Engineering Project Management. When the next semester started, the proposed transformation was adapted and extended to two more courses with similar contents. Before the transformation, a group assignment to be delivered by the end of the semester, and an individual written test was used for assessment. After the transformation, several group assignments were used, to allow for early feedback. Instead of one individual written test, several individual quizzes were introduced to distribute the learning assessment throughout the semester. A total of 93 students participated in this experience, and 55% answered a questionnaire at the end, used to collect feedback. The main conclusion of this study is that 57% of the students who answered the questionnaire preferred several group assignments during the semester instead of just one to be delivered at the end, and 92% of the students preferred several quizzes throughout the semester. Open questions were also made and the main results are presented in the paper. This experience can serve as a reference for colleagues who want to change their assessment methods to help students have better learning experiences.

Keywords: Assessment Methods; Engineering Education; Project Management.

1 Introduction

This paper presents an endeavor aimed at transforming the assessment methodology of three distinct curricular units within the field of project management at the University of Minho, offered to various engineering courses. Specifically, it addresses the Integrated Project Management (Int.PM) course within the Master in Engineering Project Management (MEPM) and Master in Chemical and Biological Engineering (MCBE), as well as Industrial Project Management (Ind.PM) course within the Master in Industrial Engineering and Management (MIEM).

This initiative commenced with the author's involvement in a pedagogical endeavor fostered by the IDEA-UMinho Centre, known as Assessment+. During this program, a range of assessment methodologies was introduced, prompting participants to evaluate a specific curricular unit and propose alterations to its assessment approach. The chosen focus was the Int.PM course within the MEPM program. Subsequently, upon the commencement of the subsequent semester, the proposed alterations were adapted and expanded to include two additional courses with similar subject matter.

This transformative experience serves as a resource for colleagues seeking to enhance their assessment methodologies, ultimately aiming to enrich students' learning experiences.

After this introduction (Section 1), a literature review on the topic is presented (Section 2). Section 3 presents the methodology used and section 4 the results obtained and a discussion. Section 5 concludes the paper, section 6 acknowledges the support and section 7 presents the references used.

2 Literature Review

Several studies on teaching pedagogy point to the advantages of changing from a traditional teaching paradigm focused on the teacher (traditional lecture method, teaching by telling approach or exposition-centered approach), in which the teacher talks and the students listen, to a teaching paradigm focused on the student and called active learning (or constructivist approach) (Freeman et al., 2014; Handelsman et al., 2004), in which the students, in addition to listening, must also read, write, discuss or get involved in solving problems, thus promoting their capacity for analysis, synthesis and evaluation (Bonwell & Eison, 1991).

To be successful in preparing our students for the future, the authors Wallner et al. (2016) suggest considering the following: enable and support our students' ability to self-organize; future challenges are increasingly interdisciplinary; individual learning processes require individual assessments; we are not the only holders of knowledge, the information our students need is abundant and available everywhere; transforming the available information into useful individual knowledge requires meta-knowledge and methodological skills, our experience enables us to help our students in this process; learning should be seen as a joint activity. We have to open up our universities and invite students to use this space as a place for meetings and discussion. We have to create the right social settings where students can discuss and work on real-life problems, which are preferably directly related to the world they live in.

Puncreobutr (2016) lists what he considers to be the key skills for the Education 4.0 era. In addition to the 21st century skills (leadership, collaboration, creativity, digital literacy, effective communication, emotional intelligence, entrepreneurship, global citizenship, problem-solving skills and teamwork), he also list the skills that make it possible to build smart nations or smart people with critical thinking, such as creativity and innovation, intercultural understanding, media and information literacy and, finally, career and apprenticeship skills. These can give us some clues as to the skills we need to help develop in our students.

To develop these skills we can use methods such as (Puncreobutr, 2016): organizing the learning process in real contexts (Zhao, 2012); organizing teaching in 4 different ways, 1) based on critique, 2) based on creativity, 3) based on productivity, and 4) based on responsibility (Sinlarat, 2016); use constructivist learning, based on the 3R, 3I and 3P phases, 3R is related to regulating understanding, which consists of Recall, Relate, Refine, 3I is related to investigating and consists of Inquire, Interact, Interpret, and 3P is related to producing, creating work by Participating, Processing and Presenting (Gomaratat, 2015); using social & virtual learning, learning based on social media, in large groups and in a virtual environment (Jeschke & Heinze, 2014).

Some tools that can be used now or in the near future are also mentioned: visual learning, social media, game-based learning, connectivity, project-based learning, mobile technologies, among others (Puncreobutr, 2016).

Evans (2013) presented a study concerning assessment feedback in higher education (HE). Through an exhaustive literature review, the concept of the feedback landscape, influenced by sociocultural and socio-critical perspectives, is formulated and presented as a framework for assessment feedback in HE. The feedback landscape focuses on process and individual development from both student and lecturer perspectives. Feedback can be perceived either as a consequence of performance or as an integral part of the learning process, fostering continuous improvement and future learning. Additionally, assessment feedback can be motivational, reinforcing, or informational, aiming to enhance performance and facilitate knowledge transfer. Feedback plays a crucial role in HE, aiding students in becoming independent learners and shaping their

professional identities. It can be done in different ways, like electronic assessment feedback (EAF), self-assessment feedback, and peer assessment feedback. EAF, delivered through various digital technologies, is praised for its potential to deepen learning approaches and enhance student achievement, although its impact on student engagement and performance varies. Self-assessment feedback is considered vital for promoting self-regulation, but there are challenges in developing students' self-assessment skills effectively. Peer assessment feedback is seen as motivational and conducive to metacognitive development, although its benefits can be variable and depend on factors such as student readiness and the quality of feedback provided. Training in the use of feedback methods, ongoing support, and alignment with learning objectives are highlighted as crucial elements for maximizing the effectiveness of these feedback approaches.

Pereira et al. (2016) reviewed research on assessment and evaluation in higher education, identifying several methods including examinations, multiple-choice tests, coursework, portfolios, digital and paper diaries, group summative assessments, oral presentations, and written assessments. Their findings indicated that most studies emphasize portfolio assessment, followed by written exams, oral exams, group assessments, and both paper and digital diaries. In terms of assessment modes, the majority of research focuses on self- and peer-assessment, followed by formative, continuous, and summative assessments. When examining assessment for specific teaching and learning methods, studies primarily address portfolio assessment, group work assessment, problem-solving and project-led education, alternative assessment methods, and online environments. The researchers concluded that students benefit from a variety of assessment practices beyond traditional written tests.

3 Methodology

The methodology used for this study was multiple case study. The focus was in three project management curricular units at University of Minho, namely Int.PM of the MEPM and the MQBE, and Ind.PM of the MIEM. After the author's participation in Assessment+, an initiative of IDEA-UMinho Centre to promote teaching and learning, a proposal of transforming the assessment method was made and in the next semester, implemented in these three cases. At the beginning of the semester the students were informed that this was an experience aiming to access if changing the assessment method was positive to the students, and that at the end of the semester they would answer a questionnaire concerning the assessment methods and their opinion on the change.

Prior to the transformation, assessment primarily relied on a single group assignment due at the semester's conclusion, alongside an individual written examination. Post-transformation, a series of group assignments were implemented to facilitate early feedback mechanisms. Furthermore, the traditional singular written test was replaced with multiple individual quizzes distributed throughout the semester.

In the Int.PM course, for the MEPM and the MQBE, the weight of the group assignments was 60%, and the weight of the individual quizzes was 40%. The group assignments for the MQBE were 3 presentations, a project management simulation game, and a final delivery assignment, and for the MEPM there was one more presentation, the rest being the same. As for the individual quizzes, there were 4 in both programs.

In the Ind.PM course, for the MIEM, the weight of the group assignments was 75%, and the weight of the individual quizzes was 25%. The group assignments included 7 deliverables (including 2 presentations) and the individual assessment included 3 quizzes.

The structure of the questionnaire was the same for the three courses, except for question 5, that was only made to MEPM and MQBE.

It included the following multiple-choice questions:

1. I prefer group work:
 - a. With a presentation and a final delivery.
 - b. With presentations and deliveries throughout the semester.
2. I prefer individual assessment:
 - a. With several quizzes throughout the semester.
 - b. In a single final test.

And the following open-ended questions:

3. Comments on how the group work went (what went well/bad, different suggestions).
4. Comments on how the quizzes went (what went well/poorly, different suggestions).
5. What is your opinion of the class with the Project Management Simulator? (only for MEPM and MQBE).
6. What is your general opinion of Int.PM/Ind.PM?
7. What is your opinion about the teacher?
8. Suggestions for improvement.

A cohort of 93 students partook in this initiative, with 55% of them (51 students) providing feedback through a post-experience questionnaire. The feedback was anonymous.

4 Results and Discussion

The primary findings of this study indicates that 57% of respondents favored the incorporation of multiple group assignments throughout the semester as opposed to a single assignment at the term's end. Additionally, an overwhelming 92% of students expressed a preference for the integration of several quizzes distributed across the semester to assess learning progress (see results in Figure 1). These are the results of questions 1 and 2 (see section 3).

Figure 1. Results for the results preferences concerning group assignments and individual assessment

Open-ended questions were also administered, yielding further insights.

As for the comments on how the group work went, of the 51 students that answered, 2 considered it went very well, 26 considered it went well, 2 considered it went normally and 21 reported different opinions and some difficulties. Some of the comments of the students were: "I think the group work went very well, all the members carried out the assigned tasks and there was a lot of mutual help"; "I really liked the assessment methodology used, I believe that with assignments over the course of the semester, you learn more than a final assignment, in other words, students will be more involved in the content covered"; "The group work went well, the presentations distributed in this way helped us to always understand the doubts of the moment and helped us to assimilate the information from one week to the next"; "I think it went well, as we did throughout the semester, I felt that the workload wasn't too much and I was able to clear up any doubts, honestly, I liked it"; "I

found it challenging and it promoted autonomy and self-learning"; "Unfortunately, we don't always contribute in the same way and with the same commitment to the work, but I still think the balance is positive"; "I think the number of papers and presentations should be reduced, I would suggest only 1 intermediate presentation"; "We had some problems using the software"; "Often the work is so presentation-oriented that the knowledge, the learning, the work done by the groups is no longer assessed, but rather the way things are presented and the ability of the groups to do so, which is also important, but which creates alienation from the course content". The opinions expressed in this question were in majority positive and reinforce that the use of several group assignments as positive, although some difficulties have been pointed out.

As for the comments on how the quizzes went, of the 51 students that answered, 3 considered it went very well, 28 considered it went well, 3 considered it went normally and 17 reported different opinions and some difficulties. Some of the comments of the students were: "In my opinion, it was the part of the course that went best, the fact that we have to study systematically helps us learn"; "I think that the division of the quizzes went very well, it makes it easier for the students to learn and understand the content taught"; "It's a good idea to separate them into parts so that you can go deeper into each topic"; "The quizzes were interesting, as a single test would have been too heavy in terms of content"; "They allowed us to have knowledge and continuous study of the subject taught"; "I think it went well, in the sense that the teacher was always very understanding and flexible when it came to resolving possible setbacks and technical difficulties"; "The first quiz was difficult by the fact that it was quite theoretical, but the others were ok"; "It should be possible to skip questions and come back to them later"; "I suggest not waiting for the late students to arrive... when the planned time arrives, the quiz should begin"; "As a working student not all of them went well for me because of certain doubts I had when I wasn't at the beginning of the lesson, and studying on my own wasn't always successful"; "Some quizzes were too long, so I'd prefer just one final test with 2 hours, for example"; "The teacher could have made the correction of each quiz available". These results reinforce that several quizzes is better than one test at the final of the semester. These quizzes were made via Blackboard, and some technical difficulties were reported, but generally they went well.

The class with the Project Management Simulator was only for MEPM and MQBE students, and there were 33 answers. Some of the most representative answers were: "An interesting class that allowed us to put our knowledge into practice"; "Dynamic lessons and a fun way to learn"; "Interesting tool for understanding the work routines of project managers"; "I got a sense of what's yet to come on a professional level"; "Good for growing group spirit and time management"; "It was really fun and educational"; "A different, more dynamic lesson that helped to understand the various concepts"; "I liked it! It was something different from what I've done at any other curricular unit"; "It was fun, but because the time was short, some details were missed"; "Very interesting, I would have liked to learn more about the tool". The feedback concerning the project management simulator was really good, so it will be a practice to keep.

Concerning the question about the general opinion about the course Int.PM/Ind.PM, some of the most representative answers were: "A very enriching curricular unit"; "Very interesting course with a practical project management component throughout the semester"; "Subject that covers relevant concepts"; "In all areas of life there are projects, so it's important to be aware of how to manage a project"; "I really enjoyed it; it was my favorite course from the beginning to the end of the semester, I think I learned a lot in this course and project management has become my main area of interest for the job market"; "The course was interesting because of its scope and the fact that we had never had anything like it before, continuous assessment led to better performance"; "It's an interesting and useful topic for carrying out and managing future projects, essential for successfully achieving your goals"; "I think it was an interesting subject, and it allowed me to get to know the reality of project management and how complex this world is"; "I liked it, even though it was a bit of a challenge

and always required a lot of commitment"; "It's a complex subject, with many new concepts, but very pertinent since it's a cross-cutting theme in any work environment, it was interesting to get a deeper insight into the topics covered, it's certainly a professional reality in our area, so I think it was very enlightening and motivating"; "I found it an interesting course and the information I learned is easily applicable, from the most basic day-to-day tasks to university and work projects"; "Before this course, I had never talked about many concepts or ways of managing a team, I thought it was an interesting subject and different from what I usually do in my program, so I felt it was an asset, I especially liked the more dynamic classes, doing group tasks"; "Interesting curricular unit, but a little complex to be given in one semester"; "I liked the course, it was interesting, but because of all the presentations and quizzes it was very hard work". The feedback relating the course was really good, and this feedback an incentive to continue improving in the future.

The most representative answers related to the opinion about the teacher where the following: "Very helpful and an excellent professional"; "Always willing to help and advice in the best way"; "Dynamic way to taught the students"; "A competent professional with a great deal of knowledge of the subject"; "Explains quite well"; "Very attentive and concerned about the students"; "The teacher proved to be an excellent professional in terms of her commitment to teaching the content, but also in monitoring the students"; "Friendly, concerned about the students, attentive and above all the availability she offers"; "Excellent, very good and interactive tutor"; "She is respectful, attentive, available and committed to the best for her students"; "Very helpful, always responded very quickly and always helped"; "The teacher was always willing to help the groups, and the feedback was always very constructive, in addition, the teacher was always very attentive"; "I thought the teacher conveyed the subject well, emphasized what was most important and managed to make a group that had no contact with project management understand this complex work"; "It was a pleasure to be your student and learn from your experience! I like the atmosphere you create in the classroom, because it makes the students more comfortable (even to make mistakes), and the presentation moments are more like learning moments"; "Your interest in the subject stimulates the students' interest"; "Teacher concerned about the students, however, the lessons were sometimes monotonous"; "She was very attentive to the mistakes made in the assignments"; "Sometimes she gives unobjective information". Concerning this feedback, I can reinforce that it is a pleasure to teach these courses, to these students. All the opinions are important, but it is good to know that the majority of them are very positive. The less positive ones are also important to encourage improvement.

Finally, suggestions for improvement were required to the students. Nothing to point out or I was satisfied was the response of 8 students. Some of the other most representative answers were: "More exercises solved in class"; "Assessment in a final test only"; "There are a lot of assignments, especially for working students, and this can make it very difficult to continue in the Master's program"; "Greater support in the use of the project software tool"; "Decrease the time of the quizzes or have only one final test"; "Make the corrected quizzes available and perhaps reduce the number of presentations, considering only the delivery of the work"; "Perhaps fewer presentations"; "I support the idea of continuous work, but maybe I'd like it better if the presentations were every two weeks... that would help the students lighten their workload"; "Slides in Portuguese; it's easier to study"; "I would just suggest that, at the end of some lessons, we spend a bit of time getting to grips with the project software in the classroom"; "In my view, the evaluation of this course is very fair given the complexity of the concepts"; "Some classes should be more dynamic"; "Dividing the assessment of the course into many assignments and tests can be positive, as long as the time needed to complete them is related to the final percentage of the course grade. I felt that throughout the semester the total number of hours spent on this subject was much higher than any other subject, because each assessment required a lot of time, especially the presentations, for too small a percentage of the final grade". These final suggestions have very important information that may help to improve even more in the future.

Considering all the results obtained, transforming the assessment method in these three project management courses at the University of Minho—specifically changing a single group assignment at the end of the semester into multiple group assignments and a single final test into several quizzes—proved to be well received by the majority of students and increased satisfaction. However, some students felt it was too much work. Therefore, an intermediate solution, balancing one test and one group assignment with several quizzes and group assignments, could be more effective and will be tested in the future. The project management simulation game was particularly well received by students, and thus, it will continue to be used.

5 Conclusion

This paper describes the transformation of assessment methods for three curricular units focused on project management at the University of Minho. The author participated in the Assessment+ initiative, where various assessment methods were introduced. The chosen transformation was implemented in the Integrated Project Management course of the Master in Engineering Project Management and later extended to two other courses with similar content. Before the transformation, assessment relied on a final group assignment and an individual written test. After the transformation, multiple group assignments were introduced to allow for early feedback, and individual quizzes were spread throughout the semester. Feedback from 93 participating students revealed a preference for multiple group assignments (57%) and multiple quizzes (92%) throughout the semester. The paper provides insights and results from this experience, offering a model for colleagues seeking to improve their assessment methods to enhance student learning experiences.

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